

PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN PLACENTAL INSUFFICIENCY

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Considering that the use of the term placenta (inflammation of the placenta) without giving the anatomical and histological name of the foci of inflammation in the placental tissue is absolutely wrong, and recommending not to use this term in the clinic, it is correct that it is possible to have perfect information when the placenta is referred to by the anatomic-morphological name of the placenta undergoing a specific inflammatory process. We know depending on the location of the inflammatory process in the placenta, the following forms of inflammation are distinguished.

Intervillitis is an inflammatory process that occurs in the spaces between the teats. Depending on the place of distribution, the following types are found: subchorial - located under the chorionic plate in a sliced state, it is composed of many leukocyte aggregates and fibrin; central - inflammatory conditions located far from the basal and chorionic plates; basal - inflammatory conditions located on the basal plate.

Villuitis (villus-vorsina-surgich) - inflammation of the nipples, in turn inflammation of the terminal nipples becomes terminal villitis and inflammation of the core nipples turns into core villuitis.

Basal deciduit - inflammation of the basal plate. It is accompanied by leukocyte infiltration, dystrophy and necrotic changes of decidual cells, wall of spiral arteries and veins, proliferation of vascular wall.

Placental chorioamnionitis - chorionic plate inflammation is often combined with subchorial intervillitis and umbilical vascular inflammation. Arterial and venous blood vessels are also damaged.

Funiculitis - inflammation of blood vessels in the navel. Macroscopically, funiculitis may not appear in some cases. Microscopically, it is often manifested in the form of phlebitis, arteritis and perivasculitis. The above cases are observed in the form of infiltration of the umbilical vascular wall and the umbilical system with a mixture of leukocytes and lymphocytes. In most cases, leukocyte infiltration does not reach the epithelial layers of the navel.

Inflammation outside the placental layers is called membranitis, and parietal amniochorioid deciduit - the inflammatory process is manifested when it covers three layers, that is, the amnion, the smooth chorion and the true separating membranes are inflamed.

Parietal chorioamnionitis (chorioid deciduit) is called when two layers are affected, parietal amnionitis or deciduit is called when each layer is inflamed separately. "Chorioamnionitis" is considered a morphological term, and clinically it is called "infected amnion syndrome".

As in other parts of the placenta, inflammation of the placental layers is caused by leukocytic infiltration of the intrauterine fluid surrounding the fetus or damage to decidual cells in the parietal layer. Since the remaining two layers of the mature placenta are not avascular, they are infiltrated by leukocytes of the mother's blood in the capillaries of the membrane separated from the placenta.

Ways of entry and spread of infection.

Infections enter the placenta by ascending routes, hematogenous routes and descending routes. Among these, the most common is through the ascending route, that is, the pathogens enter the amniotic cavity through the cervical canal from the vagina. Such cases are often manifested by premature rupture of the amniotic membrane and the discharge of amniotic fluid. But an intact amniotic membrane cannot be an insurmountable obstacle. Lesions in this case usually occur in the last hours of intranatal or antenatal periods.

Pathologies typical of inflammatory processes arising in the placenta through ascending pathways: amnionitis, chorionitis, chorioamnionitis, intervillousitis, deciduitis and funiculitis (amniotic type of inflammation). Pathologies typical of inflammatory processes occurring in the fetus through the ascending pathways: in most areas of the surface layer of the skin and mucous membranes, all areas where the intra-shell liquid directly surrounds the fetus, respiratory tract, alveolar tract, alveoli and gastrointestinal tract.

In the case of hematogenous damage of the placenta, it is observed that infectious agents from the mother's blood enter the separated layer of the placenta, placental tissue through the spiral arteries, or enter the actual separated layer of the placenta through the endometrial blood vessels.

This process of infection often occurs antenatally. Pathologies specific to this condition include villitis, subchorial intervillitis, basal deciduitis, and inflammation of umbilical blood vessels.

Pathologies specific to hematogenous damage to the fetus include: damage to organs - in particular, organs with a large supply of blood and organs that are not limited to the external environment: liver, adrenal gland, kidney, spleen, etc. enters. Inflammation due to infection through the descending tract depends on which part of the placenta is located near the opening of the fallopian tube. Mixed routes of infection can also be observed, in such cases, the process often begins via ascending routes or hematogenous routes.

Consequences for the fetus. Infection of the placental layers causes premature birth of the fetus and local and diffuse purulent-inflammatory diseases due to infection of the fetus or the newborn baby. Limited chorioamnionitis may not have clinical manifestations. Perivillitis is manifested by the fact that the fetus has stopped growing.

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